

Robot supported Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing - Parameter studies on dot-by-dot printed structures using carbon steel and different shielding gases

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ABSTRACT

Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM) is a robot-controlled welding process used to build up three-dimensional structures in steel. Like other Additive Manufacturing (AM) technologies, WAAM allows for geometrically complex structures to be manufactured which may be unfeasible to manufacture using conventional methods. Over recent years, WAAM has also gained prominence in the fields of architecture and civil engineering, with applications ranging from fully printed steel bridges to individualized steel components. This paper presents a workflow from design to manufacturing to destructive material testing of specimens for the use of WAAM with dot-by-dot printing. In a comprehensive parameter study, welding and process parameters for vertical structures are presented and investigated. The focus is on the influence of different shielding gases, the diameter of the wire electrode and the influence of the cooling of the structures during manufacturing. In a first step, the parameters are assessed and evaluated in regard to the geometric properties of the printed layers, as well as material and energy consumption. Finally, destructive tensile material tests of as-built test specimens provide a statement on the material characteristics and thus the suitability for future use in the additive manufacturing of complex lattice column structures.

Keywords: Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing, dot-by-dot printing, parameter study, lattice columns

1 INTRODUCTION

In contemporary architectural endeavours, buildings not only fulfil functional necessities but also serve as representatives of societal ideals and aspirations. The imperative for architectural innovation mandates a departure from standardized approaches, necessitating the integration of bespoke structures alongside conventional elements. Although modern steel fabrication techniques allow for some degree of customization, the process remains laborious, costly, and time intensive. Moreover, the escalating scarcity of skilled labour underscores the imperative for increased automation within the industry. As a preliminary step towards automation, fully automated I-beam production lines have been introduced, albeit predominantly utilized by specialized steel fabrication firms globally. Despite the prevailing reliance on traditional fabrication methods, the advent of Additive Manufacturing (AM) heralds promising prospects for the sector, particularly in terms of individualization and automation across diverse applications (1). AM, however, has yet to gain full traction within the steel construction domain. While Additive Manufacturing employing Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM) predominantly focuses on continuous welding processes, the feasibility and efficacy of dot-by-dot WAAM applications warrant further scrutiny. Given the static or minimal movement of the welding torch during material deposition, conventional metrics such as Travel-Speed (TS), Wire-Feed Speed (WFS) or WFS/TS-ratio prove inadequate for ensuring similar seam geometric behaviour and targeted process stability. Consequently, novel parameter studies for welding and process parameters are necessary to comprehend the influence of these parameters on the solidification of the molten pool and material properties. This study endeavours to address this critical knowledge gap by conducting comprehensive investigations into a spectrum of welding and process parameters as well as changing shielding-gases. By elucidating the interplay between geometric intricacies, process stability, and material strength, this research aims to augment the understanding of dot-by-dot printing

with mild carbon steel. Such insights hold the opportunity to increase the potential of WAAM for the steel construction industry.

2 WIRE ARC ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING

2.1 Process description

Within the steel construction industry, the research in Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM) has raised attention. WAAM is an additive manufacturing process based on gas shielded metal arc welding (GMAW). The electric arc (mostly short arc and spray arc) melts the welding wire which serves as the printing material. The liquid molten pool solidifies in lines or spots which can be classified as continuous or discrete (also known as point-by-point or dot-by-dot welding) and forms three-dimensional structures. The shielding gas protects the material deposition from atmospheric influences and impurities. At the same time, it stabilizes the heat input of the welding process and influences the molten pool (2). The degree of viscosity, the length and kind of active and passive cooling and thus the solidification process are decisive for the geometric shape of the seam, the target geometry and the material characteristics. The selection of the wire electrode significantly determines the material characteristics of the manufactured structure. Six-axis robotic systems, like the one at the laboratory of the Technical University of Darmstadt, given in Fig. 1, for guiding the welding torch offer great flexibility in the manufacturing of components and are used to ensure production in large installation spaces. With increasing size, accuracy decreases as the distance to the machine origin extends (3). To avoid inaccuracies large structures might be divided in segments to be manufactured simultaneously. At the same time, WAAM offers higher deposition rates compared to other metallic additive manufacturing processes and investment costs for supplies and system technology are significantly lower (4). These aspects make the process attractive for the manufacturing of large structural components like free form columns and its single components.

Fig. 1 a) Material deposition of continuous welding in detail; b) WAAM-system at TU Darmstadt

2.2 Dot-by-dot printing

In contrast to the conventional method of layer-by-layer deposition to form solid structures, dot-by-dot printing represents a discrete material deposition process used in WAAM. This approach necessitates an intermediate cooling interval between successive layers to facilitate the solidification of each deposited droplet. Initial applications of this technique have involved the manufacturing of self-supporting bars for use as linear reinforcements in concrete structures (5–7), as well as to join non-touching parts during the assembly of steel elements (9), and in the creation of lattice structures (10, 11). Recent efforts have focused on refining process parameters and path-planning strategies (9, 11). Furthermore, investigations into the material behaviour of dot-by-dot printed structures utilizing mild carbon steel wire electrodes (ER70S-6) with wire diameters ranging from 0.8 mm to 1.2 mm and using shielding gases M21 and Ar85C14 have been undertaken. These studies, conducted using Cold Metal Transfer (CMT) and CMT Cycle Step welding processes, aim to determine the mechanical properties, including strength and elongation properties, of the resulting materials (5, 6, 7, 12). Similar analyses were also carried out with the stainless steel ER 308LSi (10).

2.3 Cooling methods for WAAM

In the domain of Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM), the cooling phase emerges as a pivotal determinant of both manufacturing efficiency and process stability. Given the inherently slow cooling rate associated with natural cooling via heat radiation (NC = Natural Cooling) and heat flux into the component, researchers have sought alternative cooling strategies to expedite the solidification process. Investigations have thus delved into the efficacy of cooling with water baths, aiming to accelerate the cooling kinetics and enhance overall productivity (13, 14). Furthermore, there is a discernible shift towards the adoption of compressed air cooling (AC) or compressed air-aerosol mixtures (WAC) within the WAAM paradigm. This trend is underscored by a nuanced approach to cooling, delineated into stationary cooling between successive welding layers (14-16) and AC or WAC cooling following the welding torch process (14, 17). The strategic deployment of these cooling mechanisms assumes paramount importance in regulating the interlayer temperature - a critical parameter described in EN ISO 13916-2017. This temperature metric characterizes the temperature gradient across successive weld layers and the adjacent base metal immediately prior to the commencement of welding for the subsequent layer. Such meticulous temperature control is instrumental in shaping seam geometry and material properties within the additive manufacturing process. Prior investigations into the utilization of different wire electrodes have yielded promising results, with limited discernible adverse effects on material properties, particularly when coupled with compressed air cooling or compressed air-aerosol mixtures (13, 15, 16). This body of research underscores the compatibility and efficacy of these cooling methodologies in mitigating potential deleterious effects on material integrity, thereby bolstering the case for their continued integration into the WAAM framework.

3 PARAMETER STUDIES

3.1 Methodology

The paper first presents the workflow followed to manufacture short vertically printed struts of 20 layers to investigate and analyze welding and process parameters for dot-by-dot printing with WAAM. In a second step the relevant parameters are described. Then the results of geometric behavior, material and energy consumption are illustrated to give a solid statement of the influence of different parameters to the dot-by-dot printing process.

3.2 Manufacturing Process

While continuous welding is a quite known process the discrete dot-by-dot welding process follows some slightly diverging steps for the deposition of a droplet of material on top of an already solidified layer. For the deposition of the material each iteration follows the repeating actions illustrated in Fig. 2. First the robot moves to the target centre point on the surface of the previous layer to achieve a consistent CTWD of 12 mm followed by a gas pre-flow phase to ensure protection from atmospheric influences. Then the arc process is ignited. While the arc process is on, the robot stays at its position for a defined welding interval (dwell time to achieve the desired vertical build-up direction until the arc process ends. While the molten pool still solidifies the gas post-flow still covers the weld. For

Fig. 2 Principal illustration of material deposition interval for dot-by-dot printing

the parameter studies the discrete material deposition is repeated for 20 layers (Fig. 3). The parameters were printed in groups of 5 specimen struts, where the grouped elements vary in their length of the welding interval. After the five welding intervals each strut's height gets measured using the TouchSense method provided by Fronius to extract each layer height. The measuring interval also provides a sufficient period for each strut to cool down naturally also benefiting from the cooling effect of the substrate plate. It provided an interlayer temperature below 150 °C (controlled with a pyrometer every 5 layers) which has been turning out to be favourable in terms of process stability and material properties. Each first two layers of a strut are recorded in scope-modus (high frequent recording rate of 3200 Hz) with a WeldScanner P1000 DV 25 GAS30110b of the company HKS to provide information about consumables, energy input (by extracting current and voltage values). After completing the parameter group, the width of the bar stubs is measured evenly distributed over the height using a calliper.

Fig. 3 Exemplary parameter set of vertical struts after printing 20 layers
Parameter: CMT_C6X1_WFS_6 welding time 0.3 s (left) and 1.1 s (right)

3.3 Parameters investigated

The efficacy of material deposition within a stable welding process is predominantly contingent upon the judicious selection and optimization of welding and input parameters. These parameters exert a profound influence on the geometric characteristics of the weld as well as the resultant material properties. Integral to this process control are the wire feed speed, the prescribed travel speed of the robotic system for continuous welding, or the dwell time for dot-by-dot printing. Central to the control of welding parameters is the Cold Metal Transfer (CMT) process regulation, an energy-efficient welding technique developed by Fronius. Table 1 enumerates the welding parameters pertinent to a Fronius CMT Advanced 4000 R welding source equipped with both CMT and CMT Cycle Step characteristics—features that afford precise control over material deposition. Additionally, relevant process parameters are delineated to facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the welding process. In the ensuing parameter study, the impact of the CMT and CMT Cycle-Step processes is scrutinized across a range of welding intervals, commencing from 0.3 seconds, and incrementally extending to 2.1 seconds, while varying the wire feed speeds. Given the documented influence of gas mixture on the geometric attributes of welded seams (20), the study incorporates the utilization of three shielding

Table 1. Process and input parameters for the parameter study

Process and input parameters	CMT		CMT Cycle Step	
	Variable	Unit	Variable	Unit
Welding characteristic		1826		1840
Number of CMT-Cycles	-		25	
Pause time	-		100	ms
Wire-Feed-Speed (set)	3.0, 6.0, 9.0	m/min	3.0, 6.0, 9.0	m/min
Welding interval (set)	0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9, 1.1	s	0.3 – 2.1	
Gas-set	15 l/min (pre-flow 1.2 s; post-flow 1.0 s)			
Wire electrode	Weko 2 G3Si1 (ER 70S-6) Ø 1.0 and 1.2 mm			
Shielding Gas	Ferroline C18	(82 % Argon, 18 % CO ₂)		
	Ferroline C6X1	(93 % Argon, 6 % CO ₂ , 1 % O ₂)		
	Inoxline C2	(98 % Argon, 2 % CO ₂)		
Welding torch orientation	0° to the vertical (neutral)			
CTWD (Contact tip to work distance)	1.20 mm			
Cooling methode	WAC	Water + Air pressure cooling		
	AC	Air pressure cooling		
	NC	Natural cooling		

Fig. 4 Evaluation of the parameter study for vertical dot-by-dot printing of struts of 20 layers using different wire diameters and shielding gases illustrated for different WFS (set) depending on the energy input per droplet gases comprising varying active gas components. In addition, two wire diameters are investigated. Evaluation of the parameter study. The results presented in Fig. 4 elucidate the correlation between energy input and key parameters such as layer heights, diameters, and wire feed rates, derived from the parameter study. The depicted trends are based on the mean values obtained from meticulous measurements. Energy input, crucial for dot-by-dot printing, is computed utilizing the following equation (1).

$$E = \int_0^{t_{weld}} U \cdot I [kJ] \quad (1)$$

This equation, a function of welding current, welding voltage (both determined by the welding characteristic curve and pre-set Wire Feed Speed (WFS)), and welding interval length, provides a quantitative assessment of the energy imparted to each welded droplet. In contrast to the conventional CMT process, the CMT Cycle Step demonstrates distinctive characteristics, notably presenting a higher layer height coupled with a significantly reduced melting rate. This distinction is discernible through the recorded WFS. The intermittent pauses of 100 ms between individual CMT intervals serve to mitigate material deposition, resulting in lower heat input and a heightened viscosity of the melt pool. When using a WFS of 3.0 m/min, maximal layer heights are consistently achieved with smaller spot diameters across all cases. The augmented melting volume associated with increased WFS consequently induces widening and, in extreme instances, reduction in layer height. The evolution of layer width exhibits an almost linear trajectory across all process parameters, attributable to localized elevations in energy input and consequent enhanced fluidity of the weld pool. However, excessive heat can compromise deposition integrity (as depicted in Fig. 2), leading to the formation of bead-like bulges. Moreover, surpassing surface tension thresholds may result in downward dripping of the liquid melt during vertical material application. Notably, an additional observation pertains to an increased susceptibility to errors throughout the welding process under these conditions. The influence of the shielding gas is also particularly evident for low wire feed rates. Here, the C6X1 and C2 achieve higher layer heights for both CMT and CMT CS with similar deposition rates, especially for the 1.2 mm wire diameter. The lower active gas content could be responsible for this. This difference decreases with higher wire feed rates and longer welding times, which suggests that the influence of the shielding gas on the layer geometry decreases as the energy introduced into the component increases. If the two wire diameters are compared, there is also a slight increase in layer height in favor of the 1.0 mm wire. This can be explained by the almost twice as high wire feed rates for the 1.0 mm wire. Although 1.0 mm wire only has a cross-sectional area of two thirds of the 1.2 equivalent, the applied volume is approximately 1.5 times greater. The two extremes in the wire feed for 1.0 mm wire must be checked again. It needs to be mentioned that all results are just based on two welding characteristics. Since the behavior of cantilevered printed parameters is also to be investigated in further research, the shielding gas C6X1 will be used in the following, as it has already proven to be advantageous in investigations into the continuous welding of cantilevered components.

4 TENSILE TESTING OF AS-BUILT STRUTS

4.1 Manufacturing of tensile specimens

The test specimens were manufactured according to the workflow described in the parameter study. In an initial preliminary investigation, the parameters CMT CS, WFS = 3.0 m/min and Welding interval = 0.7 s were selected (see Table 2). The influence of cooling methods is now included as a new component and since the behavior of cantilevered printed parameters is also to be investigated in further research, the shielding gas C6X1 will be used in the following, as it has already proven to be advantageous in investigations of the authors into the continuous welding of cantilevered components.

4.2 Test-set-up

The tests were carried out in a MAN 1000 kN hydraulic universal testing machine (UT), which is shown in Fig. 5 d). The readings of load and displacement were recorded by the UT at a rate of 0.5 Hz. The UT was set to displacement control at a rate of 1.2 mm/min and the specimens were loaded in tensile beyond the ultimate load until the point of fracture was reached. Table 2 lists the specific height of each strut and as well as the average and minimum thickness (which are given exemplary with the white mark in Fig. 5 b) and c) measured in the area of interest. The minimum value is used to calculate the stress values with the minimal cross-section area calculated with the circular cross-section. Fig. 6 illustrates the stress-strain-curves of the tested specimens divided into the thickness of both wire electrodes. The strains in Fig. 6 were determined at strains < 4.5 % using a touching extensometer with sharp callipers over the predefined initial gauge length. Strains > 4.5 % are

Table 2. Overview of the performed uniaxial tensile test series

Test series		T-RB-1	T-RB-2	T-RB-3	T-RB-4	T-RB-5	T-RB-6
Σ specimens		3*	3**	3**	3*	5**	3**
Welding and process parameters							
Wire diameter	in mm		1.00			1.20	
Shielding gas			C6X1			C6X1	
Welding process			CMT CS			CMT CS	
WFS _{parameter,measured}	in m/min		6.2 (set 6.0)			3.55 (set 6.0)	
$t_{welding,set}$	in s		0.70			0.70	
$t_{welding,measured}$	in s	3.21	3.23	3.23	3.2	3.23	3.23
Cooling method		NC	AC	WAC	NC	AC	WAC
Max.Cooling time	in s	79 ± 1	25 ± 10	25 ± 10	60 ± 4	25 ± 10	25 ± 1
Σ layer		459	468	465	450.00	930	460
$E_{droplet}$	in kJ	2.13	2.14	2.15	1.80	1.8	1.8
$T_{interlayer}^{***}$	in °C	281 ± 74	260 ± 61	210 ± 62	226 ± 58	219 ± 55	124 ± 56
Geometric properties and related parameter information							
$h_{layer,parameter}$	in mm		1.26 ± 0.25			1.22 ± 0.30	
$h_{layer,specimen}$	in mm	1.180	1.181	1.168	1.160	1.178	1.182
$h_{specimen}$	in mm	17.77	17.74	17.67	-	18.08	17.74
$t_{parameter}$	in mm		7.52 ± 0.08			7.00 ± 0.09	
$t_{average}^{***}$	in mm	7.76	7.77	7.76	7.35	6.99	7.14
t_{stddev}^{***}	in mm	0.19	0.17	0.17	0.34	0.22	0.22
t_{min}^{***}	in mm	7.49	7.43	7.41	6.85	6.53	6.70
A_{min}^{****}	in mm ²	44.02	43.32	43.09	36.80	33.44	35.22
Specimen nomenclature		T-RB-1a T-RB-1b T-RB-1c	T-RB-2a T-RB-2b T-RB-2c	T-RB-3a T-RB-3b T-RB-3c	T-RB-4a T-RB-4b T-RB-4c	T-RB-5a T-RB-5b T-RB-5c	T-RB-6a T-RB-6b T-RB-6c

* 3 specimens were manufactured parallely

** each specimen was manufactured singulary

*** data provided for the area of interest/tested

**** calculated as circular cross section based on the thickness t_{min}

measured using the machine path of the universal testing machine, so that these strains are only qualitatively meaningful. Moreover, a digital image correlation (DIC) system capable to measure strains in a predefined area of the specimens was used to give a more accurate description but the results have not been evaluated yet. This results in deviations between the elongations at break shown and the values from Table 3, which were determined on the destroyed samples in accordance with DIN EN ISO 6892-1 Eq. 6.

Fig. 5 a) Manufacturing of T-RB-3a; b) T-RB-1a backside with marks to determine fracture strain; c) T-RB-3a backside with marks to determine fracture strain; Specimen clamped in universal testing machine for tensile test with fine displacement tracker to determine the strain

4.3 Evaluation of as-built tensile specimens

The results of the tensile testing are given as stress-strain-curves in Fig. 6 and enumerated in Table 3. For both wire diameters, the uncooled specimens exhibit the lowest yield strength and ultimate strength. For T-RB-1, even the specified minimum yield strength value of 420 N/mm² is undershot. While the highest material strengths can be achieved for the 1.0 mm wire diameter for WAC, the difference between AC and WAC is very small for the 1.2 mm wire. The results scatter in the range

Fig. 6 Stress-Strain-Diagram for as-built tensile specimens manufactured using different cooling approaches and two wire diameters

of approximately ± 2 to 7 % in particular for the test series T-RB-5. It should be noted that the results are based on the assumption of a circular cross-sectional area. As a result, deviations from the actual stress in the cross-section may occur. Information on the modulus of elasticity will follow after evaluation of the DIC tests. Nevertheless, the material stiffness is approximately the same for the

Table 3 Resulting strength and fracture of strain for as-built dot-by-dot printed struts

Test series		T-RB-1	T-RB-2	T-RB-3	T-RB-4	T-RB-5	T-RB-6
Mean Area	in mm ²	47.336	47.381	47.250	42.459	38.365	40.041
Min. Area	in mm ²	44.022	43.319	43.086	33.730	33.035	35.221
Upper yield strength	in N/mm ²	391 $\pm$ 7	406 $\pm$ 15	449 $\pm$ 9	410 $\pm$ 9	464 $\pm$ 27	461 $\pm$ 34
Tensile strength	in N/mm ²	525 $\pm$ 25	533 $\pm$ 17	572 $\pm$ 12	551 $\pm$ 3	584 $\pm$ 22	577 $\pm$ 27
Fracture strain	in %	27 $\pm$ 4	26 $\pm$ 3	25 $\pm$ 2	19* $\pm$ 0	15* $\pm$ 6	19 $\pm$ 4

* at least one specimen didn't fail in the initial gauge length

linear-elastic strain range. A ductile deformation behavior is obtained for all test specimens. The measured fracture length shows a very homogeneous result at approx. 25 % for the 1.0 mm wire electrode, while the elongation for 1.2 mm is reduced to approx. 20 %. For T-RB-4 and T-RB-5, one and two specimens respectively did not fail in the marked area but also showed no weakening due to pores, for example. Compared with previous tests on mild carbon steel as-built tensile specimens (5–7, 12) which were mostly manufactured using CMT, higher material values were achieved for the yield strength and ultimate strength. In addition, the cooling approach seemed to be even more beneficial regarding material strength.

5 CONCLUSION

The presented findings on the parameters investigated for dot-by-dot printing of mild carbon steel provide a strong and promising basis for further application in the steel construction industry. Other than previous studies, this contribution set the focus on understanding the influence of welding and process parameters which are necessary and of high significance for dot-by-dot printing and different active cooling approaches. The following conclusions can be drawn based on the discussed results:

- Both CMT and CMT CS are suitable for dot-by-dot printing, whereby higher layer heights can be achieved with CMT CS.
- Shielding gases with a lower active gas content (C2 and C6X1) have a winning effect on the layer height for wire feed rates of 3.0 and 6.0 m/min. This decreases with increasing WFS.
- The achieved material properties of dot-by-dot printed WAAM-struts indicate material strength equal or higher to the wire electrodes material properties. The recorded strain values substantiate a ductile behaviour under tensile loading.
- The difference between NC and both active cooling approaches (AC and WAC) indicates beneficial effects on material strength.

Therefore, the dot-by-dot printing in WAAM using various shielding gases and active cooling approaches seems to provide great potential for further application into lattice structures or other steel structure attempts.

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